

EUCloudEdgeIoT at Enlit Europe: Innovating for a Sustainable Energy Future

EUCloudEdgeIoT's presence at Enlit Europe marks a significant step in demonstrating how Cloud, Edge, and IoT technologies are pivotal to the future of sustainable energy. This reportage delves into the initiative's groundbreaking contributions and collaborations that are reshaping the energy sector, aligning with Europe's digital and green transition goals.

ENLIT EUROPE: A CONVERGENCE OF ENERGY INNOVATION

Enlit Europe has emerged as a crucial event, gathering innovators in the energy sector. It's a platform where the latest trends, challenges, and solutions in the energy transition are brought to light.

This year's event in Paris was not only a conference but also a collaborative hub for sharing insights and forging pathways towards a decarbonized and digitalized energy future.

Enlit Europe 2023: Highlights and Key Takeaways

The 2023 edition of Enlit Europe in Paris was not only remarkable for its focus on integrating renewable energy, enhancing smart grid capabilities, and exploring digital solutions for energy management, but also for its impressive scale. With 14,000 attendees, over 700 exhibitors, and 500 speakers, the event showcased a diverse range of panels, discussions, and exhibitions. It highlighted the critical role of technological innovation in achieving sustainable energy goals and served as a vibrant platform for industry stakeholders to navigate the complexities of the energy transition and to collaborate on scalable and efficient solutions.

Showcasing Innovations at EUCloudEdgeIoT's Booth

EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu, represented by the UNLOCK-CEI project, marked its presence at Enlit Europe with a dedicated booth, highlighting the energy use cases being developed by its project community, and disseminating key CEI market trends, impacts and Value Chains of the Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum in the energy sector, recently **published in a dedicated brochure.**

The booth also showcased the EUCloudEdgeIoT community's joint activities, emphasising the role of **thematic task forces**. These task forces focus on coordinating and disseminating information among stakeholders in the Cloud, Edge, and IoT ecosystems. They aim to reduce work overlap, amplify project impacts, and identify collaboration opportunities and potential conflicts. Additionally, these efforts contribute to developing common strategies and increasing the visibility of the Cloud, Edge, and IoT continuum within the community.

Advancing Energy Solutions through Technology

Claudio De Majo, as EUCloudEdgeIoT representative, actively participated in the panel "Energy Data Spaces –Technologies" focusing on CEI-based use cases in smart grid management and renewable energy integration. His insights covered the critical role of real-time power flow optimisation and how edge computing and dataspaces are instrumental in enhancing energy management strategies.

The session shed light on the pioneering efforts of Meta-Operating Systems (MetaOS) projects in driving forward edge data center management, emphasising their solutions for data processing, analytics, and the application of AI in smart grid operations, EV charging, and maintenance using drone technology.

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Harnessing the synergy of
Cloud, Edge, and IoT to
illuminate the path towards
a sustainable and digitally
empowered Europe

EU CLOUD EDGE IOT: CATALYSING TECHNOLOGICAL SYNERGY FOR A SMARTER EUROPE

EU Cloud Edge IoT aims to create a pathway for the development of the Cloud, Edge, and IoT (CEI) Continuum.

This initiative fosters cooperation among a diverse range of stakeholders, including researchers, developers, and business users, to embrace this new technological paradigm.

EU Cloud Edge IoT emphasises the critical role of Open Source Software (OSS) and Hardware in its strategy. By promoting an open ecosystem from Cloud to Edge to IoT, it aims to empower the European industry in green and digital transformation, aligning with the objectives of the Digital Decade. The initiative also actively engages in improving and creating open standards to foster the development of interoperable smart solutions

EU Cloud Edge IoT also emphasises the critical role of Open Source Software (OSS) and hardware in its strategy. By promoting an open ecosystem from Cloud to Edge to IoT, it aims to empower the European industry in green and digital transformation, aligning with the objectives of the Digital Decade.

Photo:
The path leading
to Enlit Europe

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EUCloudEdgeIoT: Powering Europe's Sustainable Digital Future

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**Community: The European Cloud, Edge
and IoT Continuum**

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